
WORKING PAPER SERIES

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in the face of competition and consolidation

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Institutional Repository

October 2019
Aeronautics Institute of Technology
São José dos Campos, Brazil

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Abstract

This paper investigates strategic drivers of network planning of the major airlines in Brazil, with the development of a two-stage methodology to empirically identify the network-related attributes influencing their business models. Using previously conceived business model archetypes of low-cost (LCC), full-service (FSC) and regional (RGC) carriers, we estimate the decision-making dynamics regarding Brazilian carriers' network design over time. Our main contribution lies in the hypothesis that airlines' networks may be strategically designed in an evolutionary pattern, blending archetypical ones. Our results suggest imitative behavior between almost all pairs of carriers, with these behaviors being most markedly manifested as convergence of strategies between the two FSCs in the market with respect to the oldest LCC. In addition, consolidations in Brazil appear to have been dependent on the underlying business models of the participant carriers, in particular that of the carrier being acquired, which may have served as a stepping stone for the market repositioning of the acquiring airline.

Keywords: airlines; business model convergence; differentiation; imitation; econometrics.

JEL Classification: D22; L11; L93.

1. Introduction

Attracted to travel due to affordable airfares, new price-sensitive customers fueled the expansion of the low-cost carrier (LCC) business model upon its debut worldwide. While sticking to secondary airports and maintaining point-to-point operations were vital strategies in these companies' rapid growth, it did not take long for LCC markets to increasingly overlap with those of full-service carriers (FSC) (Franke, 2004; Morrell, 2005; de Wit and Zuidberg, 2012). Beginning with short-haul routes where FSCs were virtually priced out, LCCs soon began to appeal to business travelers, whose choices were increasingly price-driven and who were otherwise indifferent to choice between the LCC and FSC business models (Mason, 2001).¹ In Europe, those passengers accounted for as much as one-fifth of Ryanair's customers in 2013.² Norwegian Air Shuttle's³ and Southwest's⁴ long-haul flights further attested to the role of business travel demand in the evolution of LCCs. However, the deep linkage between business models and network structures meant that increased complexity in their operations would follow that new state of affairs.⁵

On the other side of the business spectrum, FSCs readily reacted to the LCC model. LCC subsidiaries, an early attempt to deter rival LCC forays with competitive 'fighting brands', nevertheless, have been mostly unsuccessful. Incompatibilities in the FSC and LCC business models (leading to conflicting strategies), significant differences in cost, brand confusion and cannibalization of markets have been cited as causes for their demise (Graf, 2005; Gillen and Gados, 2008). Indeed, isolated examples of successes of such strategies are said to have been caused primarily by the separated operations between the subsidiary and the parent carrier (Lindstädt and Fauser, 2004; Morrell, 2005; Whyte and Lohmann, 2015). These and other experiments carried out precisely by the companies with least financial leeway (coupled with the financial volatility that is peculiar of the air transportation industry), eventually created a rushed overhaul of the traditional FSC model. Particularly since the 2000s, FSCs have begun to adopt a set of traits from their LCC rivals⁶ with hopes of obtaining greater flexibility in their operations - mostly translated as cost-cutting, service unbundling and network restructuring initiatives. Adaptation to ever-changing market circumstances and customer needs resulted in both opposing sides converging with one another, with a somewhat 'hybrid' business model starting to insinuate itself halfway, as an integrated strategy of competition through both cost leadership and product differentiation (Lohmann and Koo, 2013).

Moreover, over time, the inevitable thickening of many regional routes and the rising average size of regional aircraft which are easily deployed on mainline routes for increased frequency of services by both FSCs and LCCs, have opened up the opportunity for the operation of markets previously

unprofitable for their business propositions (Holloway, 2008). In this way, yet a third dimension has been brought to the business model convergence issue, namely, that of the regional carrier business model (RGC). Increasingly blurred boundaries amongst the use of attributes of these various models have led to a process of hybridization, where airlines have enhanced their competitive advantages by adjusting their operations to better cater for individual markets.

In this context, by considering how typical airlines' business models set up their network structures and, having observed the actions of a set of companies during periods reflecting a given airline archetype mentality - FSC, LCC or RGC - we aim to address the issue of convergence from the perspective of an empirical network design analysis. We therefore raise the following research question: *“Given a set of archetypical business models and their corresponding network design mentalities, how do carriers' observed network behaviors conform with these archetypes?”*. To provide a better understanding of such behaviors, we further isolate the effects of competition faced and consolidations undertaken by these carriers.

In this study, Brazilian air transportation data corresponding to the period between January 2001 and December 2018 is employed, where both route and airport characteristics commonly associated with these archetypical models are considered. This particular setting is chosen given the remarkable expansions and subsequent business model adaptations of two LCCs, Gol and Azul, which took place in the country during that time. At the same time, a series of mergers and acquisitions (henceforth jointly referred to as consolidations) involving diverse combinations of business models (LCC-FSC, FSC-FSC, and LCC-RGC) also took place. Gol Airlines, the first of these carriers, devoted itself initially to the Southwest business model. In a short period of time, Gol achieved market shares that Southwest had taken decades to obtain, in the process incorporating the bankrupt legacy carrier Varig, together with its invaluable set of airport slots. The second carrier, Azul Airlines, entered the Brazilian air transportation market as an LCC with a business model which was quite distinct from Gol's. Azul's model was more in line with that of JetBlue, with an emphasis on connections and a combination of low fares and high standards of service. Its acquisition of the regional carrier Trip Airlines early on provided a change of course for the company in terms of network structure, ultimately establishing one of the largest networks of regional passenger services in the world.

The main contribution of this study lies in the development of an econometric framework to examine the ways in which business models conform to traditional archetype network mentalities, while also providing a means of evaluating the extent to which convergence or divergence has taken place between firms and their rivals. This setup, furthermore, allows us to make an inference as to which

side of the business spectrum (FSC, LCC, or RGC) convergence (if any) has occurred (Lohmann and Koo, 2013). By accounting for the influences of rivals' strategic interactions, our approach also enables us to examine the role of imitation and/or differentiation of rivals' behaviors in the shaping of these companies' market portfolios.

In addition, when considering the effects of consolidation, we further investigate the role rivals might play in a viable strategy in providing the necessary conditions for implementation and/or adaptation of business models – a way for these firms to better position themselves in the market. In this manner, they might either allow a reorientation already longed for but previously unsuccessful, or they may offer the company an off-course market opportunity worth pursuing.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. A review of the existing literature regarding airline business model convergence, including the effects of consolidation, is presented in Section 2.1. This is accompanied by a summary of research on rival behavior imitation in Section 2.2. Section 3 then provides an overview of the carriers in our sample, along with an analysis of their operational data. Section 4 specifies the research design, the data set, and the development of our empirical model. Estimation results are evaluated and discussed in Section 5, which is followed by the conclusions in Section 6.

2. Conceptual framework

2.1. Business model convergence

In the process of classifying a company as pertaining to a given business model archetype, a set of traits is usually assessed. In the case of low-cost carriers (LCCs), these traits traditionally have rested upon those of Southwest's business model in the early 1990's, with features such as short-haul flights, point-to-point route design, secondary airport-based operations, high aircraft utilization, fleet commonality, high labor productivity, single service class, unbundled fares, limited air cargo and no alliance memberships, to name a few (Holloway, 2008). These features provided a departure from those commonly associated with the full-service carrier (FSC) model, locked into practices having the greatest contrast with the LCC model, given their targeted customer base (i.e., mostly business travelers). Holloway (2008) offers a discussion on how service expectations by these carrier's primary customers have hindered their adaptation to these and others' LCC features.

In practice, however, most companies do not rigidly follow such templates. One could argue that, as airlines' products become more standardized, the most cost-efficient companies may attain the goal of consolidating their LCC image more easily in the market, thus becoming the 'go-to' company

in this niche and forcing their competitors to deviate in one way or another from the traditional model, differentiating themselves in order to survive.⁷ Mason and Morrison (2008) provide evidence for this assertion. Using a product and organizational architecture (POA) approach to the business models of six European LCCs, these authors suggest that deviations from the pure LCC traits (to which Ryanair has conformed the most) proved to be a less profitable strategy for those firms.

Daft and Albers (2013) examine the classification of airlines by a set of indices. By proposing a framework for studying business model convergence in five German airlines, their results point to convergence towards the FSC model. Similar results can also be found in a more comprehensive study by the same authors (Daft and Albers, 2015), where they additionally report that, in comparison with FSCs, LCCs tend to have higher levels of differentiation among themselves, usually as a consequence of the aggressive expansion efforts that LCCs make to attract business passengers.

Following this literature, Lohmann and Koo (2013) propose the ‘airline business model spectrum’, further examined by Jean and Lohmann (2016). Using data from major US carriers in the period from 2011 to 2013, Jean and Lohmann (2016) found evidence of the propensity for merged airlines to move towards the FSC end of the spectrum, deviating significantly from their original business models in the face of such disruptive events, while individual airlines not involved in a merger moved towards the LCC side. Also, a quantitative examination of the competitive advantages of airlines is outlined by Moir and Lohmann (2018) who, in assessing these firms’ business strategies, examined the gap between their strategic propositions and the value created by the firms themselves. The authors identified a trend in airlines with lower cost structures to maintain a higher level of competitive advantage. Nevertheless, their results suggest that this level of competitive advantage was not directly related to the analyzed companies’ business models. This is illustrated by the fact that the ultra LCC Frontier Airlines scored the second lowest overall result, i.e., had the second most significant gap.⁸

What is more, Klopheus et al. (2012), while investigating changes in European LCCs’ business models towards hybrid strategies, found that many airlines deviating from the pure LCC model did so mainly in regard to their ‘airport choice’ and ‘network strategy’ traits. Lange and Bier (2019), by employing a set of metrics from graph theory, provided further evidence of the central role of network structures in defining airlines’ business models, with European airlines with related models sharing significant similarities, mainly associated with the coverage of their networks and frequency of service. Thus such results pave the way for more econometric-oriented treatment of the business model convergence issue, based primarily on publicly available supply and demand data. An

example of such an investigation is offered by Fageda et al. (2015), who examined the market entries into the European air transportation industry throughout the summer of 2013. The authors found that different sets of route characteristics are taken into account by archetypical LCCs and hybrid airlines when configuring their networks, with a widening gap between their operations being primarily manifested in the ‘fare unbundling’ and ‘point-to-point operation’ tenets of the pure LCC model. Focusing only on a brief time period, Fageda et al.’s research was not concerned with possible ongoing changes of business models. In a similar econometric vein, although encompassing a broader interval of time, Henrickson and Wilson (2016) examined airport and route choice decisions made by legacy carriers and LCCs within the US airline industry. Using a difference-in-differences approach, they found evidence of convergence of these airlines’ strategies over the 21 years from 1993 to 2013, specifically towards the FSC side.

These results reinforce the notion that convergence is taking place in the air transportation industry within both the US and Europe, mostly manifested by LCCs moving towards the FSC side of the business spectrum, although with varying strategies - be it by network developments, higher flight frequencies, loyalty programs or in-flight amenities (Mason and Morrison, 2008; Daft and Albers, 2013; Lohmann and Koo, 2013; Jean and Lohmann, 2016; Klophaus et al., 2012; Fageda et al., 2015; Henrickson and Wilson, 2016).⁹ Further qualitative results revealed in studies by Jarach et al. (2009) in a survey of senior executives from six European airlines, emphasize that, regardless of these companies’ business models, all compete for the same passengers, of which business travelers constitute the most profitable share.

Based on the findings of the previous literature, we therefore have evidence that a carrier’s route network may gradually drift away from the archetypical baseline followed by it in its past strategies. At any given moment when revising its long-run strategies, a carrier has to decide to either remain faithful to its original archetype (or archetypes, if the carrier already maintains a ‘mixture’ of them) or to make some key adjustments - a sort of business model ‘mutation’. Given this potential strategic ‘tune-up,’ we conjecture the following:

Hypothesis H₁: *At any given time, airlines’ networks are decomposed into a blend of archetypical ones.*

With Hypothesis H₁ we aim to trace back how each company looked then, now, and every way in between the timeline of our dataset (i.e., we identify its mutational process).

We further highlight that in this research we consider the regional carrier archetype (RGC), often overlooked in previous research in this field. We contend that carriers associated with this model

present sufficiently distinctive features (indeed, to the point of forming a separate sector of the industry), being worthy of a category of their own. Features of such archetype include the use of smaller aircraft than the ones operated by FSCs or LCCs (often regional jets or turbo-prop aircraft with less than 120 seats); a focus on servicing thinner routes, mostly having shorter stage lengths than those of the other archetypes; specialization on particular geographical or market niches and avoidance of hub airports in favor of secondary and tertiary ones (Doganis, 2006; Holloway, 2008; Bilotkach and Pai, 2014). Given their fleet and cost-structure advantages in the short-haul markets, these carriers have often engaged in the provision of feeder traffic to major FSCs, linking regional airports to major hubs. In many cases, these carriers have been established as subsidiaries of these FSCs, alternatively being operated independently or as franchisees with inter-line agreements. We note, however, that in the special case of regional subsidiaries of major carriers, these are treated herein as part of the airline group to which they belong.

Lastly, given the results of Jean and Lohmann's (2016) study, we also consider the possible disruptive effect that consolidations may have had on the ongoing evolution of carriers' networks. This is because organizational and structural changes are a common companion to consolidations and, understandably, may induce extreme business model diversions. This may occur naturally (passively) or may have been previously intended by a given airline as a market repositioning strategy. With this, the company may have been aiming at a new set of markets in which to operate. However, given the role of a company's network in the setting of its brand identity and the definition of its business model (Holloway, 2008), the consolidation may have produced a much larger reorientation effect than expected. As such, we make:

Hypothesis H₂: *From the perspective of an airline's network, consolidation events have a disruptive effect on their business models, be it by facilitating reorientation needs already intended or by offering new market opportunities.*

We note, however, that in this research we do not aim to distinguish between the causes for such reorientations, focusing only on the occurrence of any network design diversion resulting from the consolidation events.

2.2. The role of imitation

While firms may differentiate themselves to gain an edge over their rivals, imitation may prove to be another valuable option for their survival. Trial-and-error approaches usually involve high costs and a significant amount of time, prompting firms (especially in highly uncertain environments) to favor mimicking the actions of competitors they perceive as being better informed about the market.

Under these circumstances, and notably on oligopolies, imitation may prove to be a means of preventing rivals from gaining undue advantage, resulting in a smaller chance of any firm succeeding or failing relative to the others, with the status quo, thus, remaining intact (Lieberman and Asaba, 2006).

In their research, Lieberman and Asaba (2006) discuss several empirical studies, the results of which provide evidence of imitative behavior. Included among those are examples from the air transportation industry, specifically associated with the literature surrounding multimarket contact. These studies find that the higher the level of multimarket contact, the lower the intensity of competition (Gimeno and Woo, 1996), the higher major airlines set their fares (Evans and Kessides, 1994), and the lower will be the rates of market entries and exits (Baum and Korn, 1996). This suggests that aggressive competition does not necessarily follow from the closest competitors. The authors nevertheless, point out that market domain *overlap* had the opposite effect (of increasing those rates). Furthermore, firms increase market similarity to rivals having similar resources and higher performance (Gimeno and Chen, 1998), with firms being more prone to match a rival's aggressive move the more dependent they are on a given market – or the more valuable the market appears to them, revealing a commitment to the preservation of the status quo (Chen and MacMillan, 1992). Hence, firms matching entry decisions to increase the degree of contact can be interpreted having a way to mitigate rivalry and/or as a way to maintain their positions relative to their rivals, thus balancing their competitive capabilities.

Based on this literature, we conjecture that an airline's market portfolio may be influenced by its learning from rivals' behaviors. In this way, besides strategic changes associated with a company's business model reconfiguration needs, we examine the extent to which mimicking rivals' network developments may have affected those firms' route choices. Our third hypothesis is presented below.

Hypothesis H₃: *Airlines' network developments, and hence their respective business model mutations, are linked to and influenced by their rivals' strategic behaviors.*

Failure to reject the null hypothesis, particularly in cases where a positive relationship is implied, would then be indicative of firms giving up being faithful to their business propositions to at least partially engage in imitation of their rivals' network choices. A result of thoughtlessly doing so would then be the widening of their strategic proposition/value creation gap. However, drawing from the discussion in the previous subsection, on the contrary, a negative relationship would suggest that these firms may have been forced to *differentiate* themselves, in response to losing their niches – be it by encompassing a hybrid strategy or even repurposing their original models.¹⁰

3. Background to the evolution of Brazilian airlines

Turning our attention to the Brazilian air transportation industry, a summary of its major carriers, their trajectories and relevant events is presented. By the end of the period under analysis (December 2018), the leading airlines, LATAM Airlines Brazil, Gol Intelligent Airlines, Azul Brazilian Airlines and Avianca Brazil, controlled the market – a clear contrast to the situation in the mid-2000s, when ‘old-timers’ Gol and (then) TAM used to dominate alone.¹¹ This situation is depicted in Figure 1, presenting the market share evolution in terms of paying passengers at the national level of the four carriers from January 2001 to December 2018. TAM and Gol reached their peak by August 2006, with 87.73% of the market.

Figure 1 - Market shares of the analyzed companies in terms of paying passengers at the national level.

Source: National Civil Aviation Agency (Agência Nacional de Aviação Civil – ANAC), with own calculations, 2001-2018.

TAM, boosted by the liberalization of the Brazilian air markets in 1998, went from a small regional carrier to the country’s biggest full-service carrier (FSC) –in the process replacing old Fokker F-50 and F-100 planes with a modern Airbus A320 family fleet. In 2010 TAM’s merger with Chilean legacy LAN gave rise to Latin America’s largest airline, LATAM. However, this merger did not significantly affect its ongoing business orientation.

Gol, Brazil’s first low-cost carrier (LCC), made its debut in 2001, rapidly growing to become a key player in the country. Its acquisition of bankrupt legacy carrier Varig by 2007, however, would shake things up, as integrating its operations with the once most important flag carrier and largest network airline in Brazil meant a definite change of course. As recently as 2017, the company strived to

reestablish its business model as an LCC, marketing itself¹² as one of “*the five largest low-cost carriers globally*” with the “*the only true low-cost carrier business model in Brazil.*”

Nevertheless, the Gol and TAM duopoly did not last long, as ‘newcomers’ Azul and Avianca arrived on the scene. Azul began operations in December 2008, entrenching itself at the São Paulo/Campinas secondary airport. From there, equipped with a fleet of Embraer E190/E195 aircraft, the company rapidly gained ground as Brazil’s leading LCC, a label later challenged by its acquisition of regional carrier Trip Airlines in 2012. All in all, the expansion of Azul’s network proved to be highly successful, as attested by its leading position in terms of the number of departures and cities served in the country, as of December 31, 2018.¹³

In 2010, Avianca Brazil was established. As the outcome of a major rebranding and business model revamp of OceanAir (founded in 2003 as a small regional carrier), the company has since successfully repositioned itself in the market, with a distinct FSC flair following its replacement of its Fokker-100 aircraft with Airbus A318s and A319s. A subsidiary of the Synergy Group, the parent company of Avianca Holdings (to which Avianca Colombia among other airlines in Latin America belong), Avianca operations in Brazil has notably been kept independent from the rest of the group since its launch. Its fast growth, a key ingredient for securing the airline a place in Star Alliance as early as July 2015, is considered to be one of the causes of its filing for bankruptcy in December 2018.

Table 1 presents a set of characteristics of these carriers related to the Brazilian air transportation industry in 2017. We note that newcomers, Azul and Avianca, reached medium-sized operations in a short timeframe, with RPK market shares of 17.8% and 12.9% respectively. Aiming at the (then) unattended niche of ‘high-quality travel experience,’ their offering of features such as free in-flight entertainment and greater seat pitch proved to be popular.¹⁴ Passenger satisfaction data suggest, though, that these companies’ realized businesses, that is, their provided levels of service, have not been on par with their value propositions, as Gol was the carrier with the least amount of complaints in that year. Furthermore, Azul, despite its high standards of service orientation, has consistently shown the lowest trip costs, proving to be a match for Gol when it comes to low-cost operations (which, in its turn, holds the lowest cost per available seat-kilometer - CASK).

Table 1 – Characteristics of the major Brazilian airlines in 2017.

Airline	LATAM	GOL	AZUL	AVIANCA
Business model-related statements (self-description)	<i>"the largest passenger and cargo airline in South America"; "significant presence in the largest hubs" "the best connectivity options"; "continually working to maintain a competitive cost structure"</i>	<i>"a low-cost carrier focused on offering low fares with high-quality customer experience"; "among the five largest low-cost carriers globally based on annual revenue"; "the lowest operating cost (CASK)"</i>	<i>"the largest network in Brazil"; "connect more passengers than our competitors"; "high-quality, differentiated travel experience"; "low-cost operating model"; "trip cost advantage relative to our main competitors"</i>	<i>"high product-quality"; "service differentials to customers, such as individual free in-flight entertainment, meals and greater space between seats"</i>
Revenues				
Total revenue (billion US\$)	4.7	3.2	2.5	1.2
Revenue - Domestic (%)	59.0%	83.8%	84.3%	96.2%
Revenue - International (%)	41.0%	15.1%	15.7%	3.8%
Revenue - Charter (%)	0.0%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%
Costs				
Total Operating Costs (billion US\$)	3.8	2.3	1.9	0.9
Costs - Labor (%)	23.9%	18.8%	20.7%	25.2%
Costs - Fuel (%)	28.9%	39.3%	30.3%	36.5%
Costs - Capital-related (%)	25.4%	24.6%	33.8%	22.6%
Costs - Fees (%)	9.0%	9.8%	8.0%	7.1%
Costs - Other (%)	12.7%	7.5%	7.2%	8.5%
Commercial Expenses per pax (US\$)	10.6	8.6	4.6	7.9
Trip Cost (thousand US\$)	17.0	9.2	7.5	10.8
CASK (US\$)	5.6	4.9	7.5	6.2
Profitability				
Total Operating Profits (billion US\$)	0.9	0.9	0.6	0.2
Gross Margin (%)	18.2%	27.0%	24.8%	19.3%
Domestic Market positioning				
Total revenue - Scheduled (billion US\$)	2.8	2.6	2.1	1.1
Revenue - Tickets (%)	84.2%	87.7%	85.9%	83.3%
Revenue - Baggage (%)	1.4%	1.5%	1.3%	1.0%
Revenue - Cargo & Mail (%)	6.6%	4.0%	2.7%	4.3%
Revenue - Ancillary Revenues (%)	7.9%	6.7%	10.1%	11.4%
Average Yield (US\$ cents)	7.8	7.0	11.2	7.9
Market share (RPK)	32.6%	36.2%	17.8%	12.9%
Average Load Factor (%)	83%	80%	80%	85%
Average Aircraft Size (seats)	173	168	109	151
Average Aircraft Age (years)	9	9	5	5
Aircraft flight hours per day	11.5	9.9	10.1	11.3
Average Stage Length (km)	984	1,014	700	1,036
Delayed Flights (%)	16%	14%	12%	18%
Number of Complaints (per 100,000 pax)	15	7	12	13
Number of Served Cities (count)	43	54	101	25
Hubs & Focus Cities	GRU, CGH, BSB, GIG	GRU, CGH, BSB, GIG, FOR	VCP, CFN, REC	GRU, BSB, SSV
Fleet size (count)	86	109	106	41
Fleet Standardization Index (HHI - model)	0.395	0.637	0.382	0.668
Fleet composition				

Sources: Statistics from the National Civil Aviation Agency (ANAC) found on the Air Transport Yearbook, the Air Transport Demand and Supply Report - Brazilian Companies, the Air Transport Statistical Database, the Flight History - Active Regular Flight (VRA), the Brazilian Aeronautical Registration (RAB), the Integrated Civil Aviation Information System (SINTAC), United States Securities and Exchange Commission Form 20-F (Gol, LATAM, Azul), and Avianca's website, at the "Who We Are" section, accessed in 12/20/2018 (www.avianca.com.br/en/quem-somos), with own calculations.

Data from Table 1 suggest that findings of the previous literature (e.g., Daft and Albers, 2013, Lohmann and Koo, 2013) may also be applicable to the Brazilian experience. As noticed, TAM evolved from a regional carrier to a top tier FSC with the establishment of LATAM, with Avianca Brazil following the same expansion pattern, from regional to mainline FSC operations (although without full integration with a major Latin American airline holding). Gol, alternatively, started as a pure LCC, having since shown some difficulty in repositioning itself again as such after the acquisition of legacy carrier Varig (not to mention its ambition in gaining a larger market share from the business travelers' segment). Lastly, Azul, although having vigorously promoted its main hub in Campinas, positioning itself as an industry maverick with low fares and a seemingly LCC behavior in its early years, became, eventually, the carrier with the highest average yield (roughly US\$ 11.2 cents, 60% higher than Gol's) and with the most significant stake in the monopoly markets of the industry's regional segment (in the wake of Trip's acquisition).

Overall, we have evidence that in the last two decades, all four carriers in Brazil have intensively adjusted their market behavior in a strategic tune-up of their business models. We believe that market characteristics and competition may have been the dominant forces of latent market profitability that gave momentum to these changes. With that in mind, our primary research purpose is, therefore, to identify, isolate and compare the key factors underlying these adjustments to these carriers' route network planning and network design which took place during that time.

4. Empirical models of network design

To implement our econometric models of network design, we used data from the National Civil Aviation Agency (ANAC) and the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística - IBGE). We employed a panel data with monthly observations of routes in the Brazilian domestic market comprising a sample period between January 2001 and December 2018, associated with the operation of carriers Gol, Azul, Avianca Brazil (formerly known as OceanAir) and LATAM (formerly TAM). These were chosen in order to examine all business model archetypes associated with the regular transportation of passengers, namely, the full-service carrier (FSC), the low-cost carrier (LCC) and the regional carrier (RGC). These are to be contrasted with other airline business models identified in the literature which do not satisfy such requirements (air cargo carriers, charter carriers, and business executive carriers). See the Appendix for details on the utilized data set.

We built all archetype mentalities using data from January 2001 to December 2005, the first five years of a genuine free market in the Brazilian air transportation industry following deregulation, a learning period during which all carriers behaved somewhat independently from each other. This timeframe provided valuable experiences for all Brazilian carriers, and hence, was critical to the fine-tuning of their identities. We note that our definitions of carriers as depictive archetypes are largely based on accounts from the general and the specialized media, how these carriers defined themselves – e.g., on reports to investors, as well as on previous research which takes this period into consideration. In this way, we chose TAM Airlines’ operations to represent our ‘full-service carrier (FSC) archetype mentality’, the Brazilian company which conformed the most to the classical FSC business model during that time. The company has been previously defined as an FSC in studies such as those by Huse and Evangelho (2007) and Oliveira and Huse (2009). Furthermore, OceanAir’s early network developments underpinned our ‘regional carrier (RGC) archetype mentality’, a period during which the company's fleet consisted mainly of aircraft with seat capacity within the 50-110 seat range. This was devised as a way to capture some characteristics commonly associated with this archetype, such as the operation of thin markets with small distances, largely confined to a particular portion of the country’s territory. Finally, for the ‘low-cost carrier (LCC) archetype mentality’, we considered Gol’s behavior during its startup period. This accounts for both strategies associated with its first months of operations, when it was heavily influenced by Southwest’s classical LCC model - mostly marked by a predominantly point-to-point network - and strategies pursued during the following years, expanding its operations to longer routes and, to some degree, incorporating hub-and-spoke network features. Gol has been previously defined as an LCC in studies such as those by Evangelho, Huse and Linhares (2005), Francis et al. (2006), Oliveira (2008), Huse and Oliveira (2012) and Koo and Lohmann (2013).

Our proposed methodology comprises two sequential stages, representing (1) the construction of idealized archetypical carriers whose network design mentalities are extrapolated to the whole Brazilian air transportation market, based on the behaviors of a set of airlines during key periods of their trajectories; and (2) the decomposition of Brazilian airlines’ actually adopted business models into mixtures of these previously constructed archetypes, all that while also accounting for possible influences of rivals, consolidation events and the mutational processes of these carriers’ business model blends. We summarize the proposed two-stage methodology for business model identification in Figure 2.

1st Stage: Archetypical network design mentalities

Figure 2 – Stages of the proposed methodology.

4.1. Stage 1 - Construction of archetypical mentalities

We employ the probit model as our main specification, following modeling undertaken by in Morrison and Winston (1990), Berry (1992), Sinclair (1995), Boguslaski et al. (2004), Dunn (2008), Oliveira (2008), Kim (2009), Liu (2009), Homsombat et al. (2014), Fu et al. (2015) and Wang et al. (2017). Furthermore, to test for the impacts of the selection of a different first-stage model on the subsequent regression analysis, we also made use of the logit model, with the works of Dresner et al. (2002), Dixit and Chintagunta (2007) and Gil-Moltó and Piga (2008) serving as examples of its applications in similar settings. In the probit framework, we set p_a to account for the presence of archetype $a \in A = \{FSC, LCC, RCG\}$ on route i and at period t . Each archetype is regressed separately with its presence on a given route being designated by the value 1. We utilize the following variables in the specification of the empirical models of this stage: *DIST*, the Vincenty distance between the endpoints of a route; $DIST^2$, the square of *DIST*; *INC*, the maximum GDP per capita between origin and destination cities of a route; and *NETWORK*, the maximum number of cities served to/from the origin and destination cities of a route. We also include regional, seasonality, and time trend terms to control for unobserved effects. Details of each variable may be found in the Appendix.

To account for the interdependence between different routes and between a route and itself in different periods, we consider temporal and spatial correlation among the observations, using probit and logit models with *two-dimension-clustered standard errors* (the interested reader is referred to Cameron et al. (2006), Guan, J. and Petersen, M. (2008), Thompson, S. B. (2011) and Cameron et al. (2011) for more details). The employed estimated standard errors clusters are city-of-origin/time and city-of-destination/time. In this way, we can account for within-airline strategy consistency, allowing for the clustering of routes that depart from or arrive at the same airport, and thus account for the interdependence between similar routes (i.e., city-pair markets) from/to the origin and destination cities at the same period. Besides, we also capture a sort of ‘incumbency power,’ due to inertial profitability of the firm maintaining its operations on a route already belonging to its network.

4.2. Stage 2 - Decomposition of airline network design drivers

Given the results of Stage 1, the estimated parameters of each archetype model are then used to extrapolate their network configuration mentalities (the estimated probabilities of presence) for all of the route observations in our dataset. The resulting variables are converted to the expected profits of their respective archetypes (as described in the Appendix), which are then employed as regressors in the carriers’ presence equations. The rationale behind this methodology is to enable a carrier’s profits to be explained by the profits that each archetypical business model would have had, had it been present at that particular route and at that particular time – thus uncovering a carrier’s ‘type’ by how its profitability is decomposed.

Furthermore, a carrier presenting a high valuation for both route groups associated with archetypes *a* and *b* would then demonstrate a hybrid network design behavior, with the inspection of the regression coefficients enabling us to assess how much of each archetype in the ‘FSC-LCC-RGC’ triad was reflected in the said carrier’s actions. On the other hand, a carrier avoiding, say, archetype *c* routes, would exhibit a divergent behavior regarding this particular archetype’s strategies. In the probit (and logit) framework(s) employed, p_c is a binary variable accounting for the presence of carrier $c \in C = \{Azul, Gol, Avianca, LATAM\}$ on route *i* and in period *t*. Differently from the first stage, here all carriers are regressed *jointly* by means of a multivariate probit model, with each of their presences being designated by the value 1. In the associated latent profit model, we set π_c^* (the latent profit of carrier ‘*c*’) with the following regressors and control variables: PR_FSC, PR_LCC and PR_RGC, the predictions from the first stage for the latent expected profit variables associated with the ‘FSC’, ‘LCC’ and ‘RGC’ archetypes, respectively; and the interactions of these predictions with consolidation event dummies (MERGER, in the cases of Gol’s, Azul’s and LATAM’s models)

and a time trend variable (TREND). The interaction variables allow us to infer to which business model archetype(s) (if any) each Brazilian carrier has converged, or to which business model(s) they remained faithful. This will reflect each company's business model blend and its mutational process, as described in **H1**, and the effects of possible disruptions associated with the consolidations, as described in **H2**. The consolidation events observed in the period were Gol's acquisition of Varig in 2007, TAM's merger with LAN in 2010 and Azul's acquisition of Trip in 2012. We also utilize regional and seasonality controls in the specification of the empirical models. Details of all variables may be found in the Appendix.

To check the robustness of our results, we utilize the probit and logit estimators with two-dimension-clustered standard errors, also employed in the first stage. These estimators are employed to address the possible effects of the relationships between the different model stages. In this way, we experiment with varying estimators across the methodological stages to check the sensitivity of the results regarding the specification of a particular model. We then tested the following combinations of models for the first and second stages: *probit-probit*, *probit-logit*, *logit-probit*, and *logit-logit*, and discuss the different estimation results.

Moreover, given our objective of investigating the role of rivals' behaviors on the analyzed carriers' network developments and due to endogeneity concerns, we opted to use as our main specification the multivariate probit model, estimated by the simulated maximum likelihood method of Butler and Moffitt (1982) and implemented by Cappellari and Jenkins (2006). In this setting, the model considers correlations between the choices made by the firms, as it accounts for the association between the unobserved determinants (the error terms) of their models. These correlations will, furthermore, enable us to test the hypothesis of rival imitation/differentiation, with statistical significance here implying that the profitability evolution of carrier, say, c is influenced by rival d 's profitability. These results will, in turn, inform us of the occurrence of either an imitation strategy (if the said term turns out to be positive) or a differentiation one (in the case of it being negative), testing the validity of **H3**.

Lastly, we point out that in alternative specifications used for checking the sensitivity of the model's results against perturbations, we inserted dummies of route presence of the existing airlines in estimators not considering a multivariate character. For each carrier, only the dummies associated with the presence of its rival airlines were included in its specification.

5. Results

5.1. Archetypical mentalities

Table 2 presents the estimation results of the archetypical network configuration models. Column (5) presents the results of our main empirical model estimation, related to the probit specification with a time trend and control variables related to seasonal and regional effects. All specifications presented make use of two-dimension-clustered standard errors at the city-of-origin/time and city-of-destination/time levels. In this way, our models are flexible enough to consider temporal and spatial correlation among the observations.

While observing the *signs* of the regressors, common ground between the FSC, the LCC, and the RGC archetypes is easily identified. Beginning with the DIST variable, all archetypes seem to share a propensity - although, with varying degrees - of serving markets associated with higher distances, a result understood in light of these routes having less competition from alternative modes of transportation (e.g., coach or train services, the latter practically unavailable in Brazil for long distance passenger transport). The nonlinear term DIST², however, provides a dampening effect on longer routes, most prominently manifested in the RGC model, for all specifications. The inclination to serve markets with an associated higher GDP *per capita* (as measured by the variable INC) also appears to be unanimous. Here, the RGC business model seems more sensible than its counterparts, an observation that we interpret as being a way in which these carriers may find to cope with thinner markets.

Concerning the NETWORK variable, the results indicate a positive influence of this variable in all archetypes. This variable provides a measure of carriers' inclination to serve routes having a highly central airport on at least one of its endpoints. We note, however, that this only implies that these airports are central to the networks of the said carrier, i.e., not necessarily central to the geographical Brazilian transportation network. The higher coefficient obtained for our LCC archetype, Gol, in comparison with that for our FSC archetype, LATAM, may be interpreted in terms of air network coverage. Given TAM's size as the largest company established in the period, the company had a greater network coverage compared to any other Brazilian carrier. This being the case, it did not have the luxury of choosing markets as its opportunities for growth were becoming increasingly scarce. The *average GDP per capita* of its markets is, thus, lower than that of the starting company (Gol), given its higher proportion of thinner markets served.

Gol, still giving its first steps during that period, preferred to enter markets with an associated higher GDP *per capita*. In its first year, the airline had not yet established itself (it had only a few aircraft)

and was still growing, choosing routes that TAM and Varig already operated instead of placing riskier bets. It sought to enter markets that maximized its network capabilities, as its smaller market share and reduced network coverage imposed significant restrictions on its possible strategies for expansion (and survival).

Table 2 – Estimation results of the 1st stage (archetypical mentalities)

	(1) 2DC Probit	(2) 2DC Logit	(3) 2DC Probit	(4) 2DC Logit	(5) 2DC Probit	(6) 2DC Logit
<u>i. FSC Archetype</u>						
DIST	0.6850***	1.1132***	0.6518***	1.0491***	0.6525***	1.0509***
DIST ²	-0.2320***	-0.3771***	-0.2269***	-0.3635***	-0.2271***	-0.3640***
INCOME	0.0656***	0.1010***	0.1374***	0.2434***	0.1339***	0.2370***
NETWORK	0.0386***	0.0631***	0.0295***	0.0469***	0.0299***	0.0476***
<u>ii. LCC Archetype</u>						
DIST	0.6076***	1.0413***	0.8596***	1.4988***	0.9509***	1.6478***
DIST ²	-0.1020***	-0.1716***	-0.2033***	-0.3542***	-0.2292***	-0.3960***
INCOME	0.1024***	0.1615***	0.0774***	0.1385***	0.1204***	0.2129***
NETWORK	0.0671***	0.1127***	0.0624***	0.1039***	0.0366***	0.0596***
<u>iii. RGC Archetype</u>						
DIST	1.3929***	2.7902***	1.2080***	2.7435***	1.7210***	4.1004***
DIST ²	-1.6501***	-3.3368***	-1.7375***	-3.7526***	-2.1622***	-4.8475***
INCOME	0.1614***	0.3370***	0.2815***	0.5760***	0.3242***	0.6610***
NETWORK	0.1092***	0.1877***	0.1095***	0.1923***	0.0639***	0.1081***
<u>Controls</u>						
Regional effects	<i>no</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>yes</i>
Seasonality & trend	<i>no</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>no</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>yes</i>
<u>Cross-equations tests of equality of parameters (chi2)</u>						
(i) FSC Arch. = (ii) LCC Arch.	821.38***	846.85***	544.60***	595.27***	389.11***	469.01***
(i) FSC Arch. = (iii) RGC Arch.	626.14***	620.38***	676.07***	708.08***	414.67***	429.05***
(ii) LCC Arch. = (iii) RGC Arch.	573.97***	491.48***	575.44***	574.92***	450.34***	454.92***
Pseudo R ² Statistic						
(i)	0.2977	0.2962	0.3355	0.3338	0.3358	0.3340
(ii)	0.3514	0.3475	0.3768	0.3734	0.3879	0.3848
(iii)	0.5314	0.5223	0.5950	0.5923	0.6333	0.6307
Nr Observations	40,292	40,292	40,292	40,292	40,292	40,292

Notes: p-value representations: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. "2DC" means Two-Dimension-Clustered Standard Errors Probit or Logit.

Concerning the results of the robustness checks reported in Columns (1) to (4) and (6) of Table 2, these indicate that the majority of variables remained statistically significant irrespective of the use of probit or logit specifications or the use of regional, seasonal or time trend controls. Moreover, they consistently showed the same signs in all specifications and, more importantly, our empirical analysis was not affected by these perturbations.

Lastly, we focus on the cross-equations tests for equality of parameters, also shown in Table 2. We note that, for all model specifications and all combination of pairs of archetypes, the tests rejected the null hypothesis of equality of parameters. In this way, these results suggest that all of the three chosen archetypes present different network design behaviors and thus produce distinct development patterns.

5.2. Network design drivers

Next, we assess the network design decompositions of the investigated Brazilian carriers. Table 3 presents the estimation results, with Column (6) presenting our preferred model, related to the multivariate probit specification with a time trend and control variables related to seasonal and regional effects. As in the first stage, all specifications presented control for two-dimension-clustered standard errors at the city-of-origin/time and city-of-destination/time levels. We note that the archetypes produced by any of the first stage estimators (probit or logit) did not provide significant changes on the coefficients of the second stage specifications, as seen in Columns (1) to (4), which test the combinations of models *probit-probit*, *probit-logit*, *logit-probit* and *logit-logit* for the two stages, respectively. A ‘pairs bootstrap’ procedure with a strata approach was also employed, consisting of 250 replications for the results of the second stage models. Results pertaining to the statistical significance of the coefficients, nevertheless, were the same as those obtained without the procedure.

Proceeding to the analysis of the model associated with Azul, its results suggest that the company’s network started as a mixture of the RGC archetype and, to a much larger extent, the LCC archetype, at least during its first months of operation. Along its trajectory, nevertheless, the company seems to have converged to the FSC archetype, as indicated by the positive coefficient associated with the corresponding trend-interacted variable ($PR_FSC \times TREND$) while diverging from its initial LCC/RGC baseline, with its LCC character reducing at a faster rate.

Table 3 – Estimation results of the 2nd stage (network design drivers)

	(1) 2DC Probit	(2) 2DC Logit	(3) 2DC Probit	(4) 2DC Logit	(5) 2DC Probit	(6) MV Probit
<u>i. Azul Airlines</u>						
PR_FSC	-0.3721***	-0.7553***	-0.2517***	-0.5053***	-0.5278***	-0.3415***
PR_LCC	1.3004***	2.4887***	0.7960***	1.5170***	1.3022***	1.3015***
PR_REG	0.0769***	0.1446***	0.0357***	0.0671***	0.0931***	0.0748***
PR_FSC × TREND	0.0035***	0.0079***	0.0023***	0.0051***	0.0043***	0.0034***
PR_LCC × TREND	-0.0124***	-0.0234***	-0.0075***	-0.0141***	-0.0132***	-0.0126***
PR_REG × TREND	-0.0010***	-0.0018***	-0.0004***	-0.0008***	-0.0011***	-0.0010***
PR_FSC × MERGER (Trip)	-0.7822***	-1.4662***	-0.4723***	-0.8778***	-0.8213***	-0.7989***
PR_LCC × MERGER (Trip)	0.2153***	0.3533***	0.1277***	0.2082***	0.2304***	0.2244***
PR_REG × MERGER (Trip)	0.0852***	0.1468***	0.0378***	0.0652***	0.0889***	0.0852***
<u>ii. Gol Airlines</u>						
PR_FSC	0.3842***	0.7462***	0.1898***	0.3807***	-0.2237***	0.4134***
PR_LCC	1.1471***	1.8919***	0.7134***	1.1784***	1.3999***	1.1156***
PR_REG	-0.0771***	-0.1359***	-0.0330***	-0.0584***	-0.0477***	-0.0630***
PR_FSC × TREND	-0.0045***	-0.0081***	-0.0028***	-0.0050***	-0.0039***	-0.0044***
PR_LCC × TREND	0.0006***	0.0010***	0.0004***	0.0007***	-0.0003	0.0007***
PR_REG × TREND	0.0003***	0.0005***	0.0001***	0.0002***	0.0002***	0.0002***
PR_FSC × MERGER (Varig)	0.2659***	0.4215***	0.1608***	0.2553***	0.2724***	0.2535***
PR_LCC × MERGER (Varig)	-0.2614***	-0.4195***	-0.1566***	-0.2515***	-0.2766***	-0.2559***
PR_REG × MERGER (Varig)	0.0001	0.0004	-0.0000	-0.0001	0.0073	0.0056
<u>iii. Avianca Airlines</u>						
PR_FSC	0.1900***	0.3418***	0.1122***	0.1993***	0.1077	0.2382***
PR_LCC	0.0576	0.1099	0.0407	0.0810*	-0.0529	0.0613***
PR_REG	0.0848***	0.1749***	0.0391***	0.0807***	0.0907***	0.0773***
PR_FSC × TREND	0.0035***	0.0062***	0.0021***	0.0037***	0.0039***	0.0032***
PR_LCC × TREND	0.0019***	0.0037***	0.0011***	0.0022***	0.0018***	0.0019***
PR_REG × TREND	-0.0004***	-0.0010***	-0.0002***	-0.0005***	-0.0004***	-0.0004***
<u>iv. Latam Airlines</u>						
PR_FSC	1.7682***	2.8986***	1.0459***	1.7122***	1.7679***	1.8452***
PR_LCC	-0.3970***	-0.6765***	-0.2209***	-0.3748***	-0.7687***	-0.3918***
PR_REG	-0.1144***	-0.1878***	-0.0504***	-0.0825***	-0.1051***	-0.1157***
PR_FSC × TREND	-0.0022***	-0.0030***	-0.0014***	-0.0019***	-0.0013***	-0.0031***
PR_LCC × TREND	0.0020***	0.0032***	0.0012***	0.0020***	0.0020***	0.0022***
PR_REG × TREND	0.0005***	0.0009***	0.0003***	0.0004***	0.0005***	0.0005***
PR_FSC × MERGER (Lan)	0.0099	-0.0032	-0.0068	-0.0248	0.1380***	0.1402***
PR_LCC × MERGER (Lan)	-0.0440**	-0.0832**	-0.0223*	-0.0423**	-0.1383***	-0.1051***
PR_REG × MERGER (Lan)	-0.0708***	-0.1165***	-0.0321***	-0.0529***	-0.0804***	-0.0708***
1 st step estimation model	2DC Probit	2DC Probit	2DC Logit	2DC Logit	2DC Probit	2DC Probit
<u>Controls</u>						
Regional effects	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Seasonality & trend	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Strategic interaction dummies	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
Pseudo R2 Statistic (i)	0.4074	0.4059	0.3930	0.3918	0.4179	
(ii)	0.2330	0.2324	0.2196	0.2188	0.3140	
(iii)	0.1855	0.1865	0.1818	0.1839	0.2075	
(iv)	0.2209	0.2193	0.2139	0.2127	0.3048	
overall						0.3766
Nr Observations	113,989	113,989	113,989	113,989	113,989	113,989

Notes: p-value representations: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$. “2DC” means Two-Dimension-Clustered Standard Errors Probit or Logit; “MV Probit” means Multivariate Probit. “PR_” means predicted values.

Gol's model indicates that the company may be best represented as majorly an LCC, although noticeably influenced by the FSC business model when performing its network design decisions. Also implied is an initial avoidance of the RGC business model archetype, as shown by the negative sign of its coefficient, indicating a negative effect on the company's latent profitability. However, over time, its business model mutational process appears to have favored a more significant proportion of this particular archetype's network characteristics, as per the trend-interacted variables – although at a much slower rate than that associated with additional convergence towards the LCC archetype.

Regarding Avianca's model, the results support the decomposition of the airline's network behavior as a mixture of the three classical archetypes, with a prevalent FSC component. Moreover, trend-interacted variables capture our *ex-ante* expectation of a decreasing alignment of the company with the RGC archetype, given its Fokker-100 fleet phaseout.

What is more, LATAM's model indicates that, while the company began predominantly as an FSC airline, avoiding RGC and LCC network strategies (see the corresponding coefficients of the archetype variables), it detached itself along the years from its FSC baseline, converging more and more towards LCC and (to a lesser extent) RGC archetypes - as per the trend-interacted variables $PR_LCC \times TREND$ and $PR_RGC \times TREND$, respectively.

5.2.1 Influences from consolidations

Turning our attention to the possible influences of the consolidation events on business models' and networks' structural breaks, we notice that no clear general pattern appears to have emerged for this set of firms, with the ensuing business orientations of the resulting airlines being dependent on the business models of their merging parts. Firstly, Gol's model implies that its acquisition of FSC Varig held back its ongoing alignment with the LCC archetype. One can argue that, having inherited Varig's airport gate and slot rights together with its frequent flyer program, the company decided to redeploy much of its resources to serve a new (and possibly more profitable) customer base. This would take place only in the short run, however, mainly due to financial restrictions for the company to set the appropriate structure to maintain the two niches. Moreover, this conjecture does find support on the rising LCC archetype trend included in Gol's model, which would cover its long-run effect. TAM's merger with LAN in 2010, associated with a deviation from the LCC and RGC archetypes, could be interpreted along the same lines, with the further remark that from a network planning point of view, their joint efforts, which resulted in Latin America's largest airline, probably brought the resulting carrier closer to the FSC archetype. On the other hand, the structural break

related to Azul's acquisition of regional carrier Trip readily agree with the discussions presented in Section 3, as it appears to be associated with a greater inclination by the resulting carrier towards the RGC archetype - compared to Azul's original business model. Based on how these results agree with our *ex-ante* expectations, we are compelled to reject neither hypothesis **H₁** nor hypothesis **H₂**, i.e., that airlines' networks can, indeed, be decomposed as a blend of archetypical ones and their business models' mutational processes can be identified and, furthermore, that the consolidation events have had disruptive effects on the ongoing orientations of these carriers.

5.2.2. Influences from rivals

The results pertaining to rival influences on each company's network design are depicted in Table 4. These results are associated with the multivariate probit specification of Column (6) in Table 3, where can be observed that the dynamics between Azul and Gol are characterized by mutual imitation to at least some degree, as indicated by the positive sign of the corresponding correlation (0.1997) found in the second row of the first column of Table 4. Similar results were obtained for the pair of rivals Azul and LATAM (0.2225) and Avianca and LATAM (0.1614). We note, however, the differences in magnitudes in these cases when compared with Gol and LATAM's rival interaction, which suggests a much stronger relationship between their network choices (0.5570). Moreover, the interaction between Avianca and Gol presents a correlation which appears to lie somewhere between these two extremes. Considering how consistently efficient Gol's operations have been during the past years (cf. Section 3), these results support the notion of firms increasing market similarity to rivals having a higher performance compared to their own (Gimeno and Chen, 1998). Another feature of these results is that they also uncover some differentiation dynamics. Avianca and Azul appear to have set themselves apart from each other. However, the magnitude of their estimated correlation, together with its associated statistical significance, imply that neither of the carriers devoted much attention to this endeavor.

Column (5) of Table 3 differs from Column (1) by the inclusion of the strategic interaction dummies (dummies of rivals). The coefficients of these dummies are not shown here, as results for strategic interactions between rivals in this model are contaminated by endogeneity issues. We only highlight the way in which the results have shown significant changes in both Gol's and Avianca's models when compared with any other specification presented.

Table 4 – Estimation results of the 2nd stage (correlations between rivals' choices)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Azul	Gol	Avianca	LATAM
(1) Azul	_____	_____	_____	_____
(2) Gol	0.1997***	_____	_____	_____
(3) Avianca	-0.0137*	0.2940***	_____	_____
(4) LATAM	0.2225***	0.5570***	0.1614***	_____

*Notes: p-value representations: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.*

Lastly, we point out that the robustness checks of Columns (1) to (4) in Table 3, which do not consider rival influences, do not differ significantly from our main model. The reproduction of the specification of Column (6) in these Columns without such rival controls was devised in an attempt to uncover any change in the analyzed companies' network design behavior arising from such influences, as a way of understanding whether failing to account for a given airline's imitation efforts of a given rival would distort its regression's results, weighting its blend more towards a particular archetype. This would mean that its business model would be less consistent, as it would deviate from its baseline model just so that it could maintain its position relative to its rival(s). The results associated with these specifications, nevertheless, did not present any significant changes from the ones shown in Column (6) in Table 3, with no coefficient's sign being altered, suggesting that none of the studied companies deviated significantly from their baseline business model so as to increase their degree of contact with a particular competitor. Together with the evidence presented in Column (6), the implications of these results compel us not to reject H_3 *in full*, i.e., our results do provide support for the linkage between airlines' network developments and their rivals' strategic behaviors, as per the correlations obtained by the multivariate probit specification. However, based on our data, we did not obtain any support for the conjecture that firms may give up being faithful to their business propositions to at least partially mirror/deviate from their rivals' network choices, as no significant alteration in their archetypical blend was detected after comparing specifications taking into account their rivals' influences with ones that did not.

6. Discussion and conclusion

This paper aimed at econometrically identifying the critical drivers regarding the network planning decisions made in the emerging airline industry in Brazil. We considered the case of Avianca, Azul, Gol, and LATAM and examined their differences concerning business models, size and market positioning, with a particular focus on their network mentalities over time. We also examined the network patterns of conceived business model archetypes.

Our proposed two-stage methodology for empirical airline business model identification consisted of a sequence of econometric models where the actual network related decisions of both the business model archetypes and the existing carriers were estimated. We considered the possibility of a dynamic network design pattern in which one of the outcomes could be that the existing networks were strategically designed as a blend of archetypical ones. We find some evidence that firms may have been influenced by their rivals, tuning their networks up in search of a greater level of market contact with them. Such results were found with respect to almost all pairs of carriers, with these behaviors being most markedly manifested as a convergence of strategies between both of the self-proclaimed FSCs in the market (LATAM and Avianca) concerning the oldest LCC, Gol Airlines. Nevertheless, our data did not support these firms doing so to the point of deviating from their business model baselines. Changing market circumstances and customer demands appear to have been more meaningful to those firms' business model blends than rivals' behaviors did.

Moreover, during the 18-year span from 2001 to 2018, many changes in the business models of the analyzed carriers and in the competitive landscape of the Brazilian air transportation industry unfolded. These changes included the bankruptcy of Varig, as well as three major consolidation events (Gol and Varig, Azul and Trip, TAM and LAN) which took place during that period. In this respect, mergers in the Brazilian aviation industry seem diverse in the way they directed the merging parts' network configurations, and hence, to some extent, their business reorientations. These appear to have been dependent on the underlying business models (or business model blends) of the participant carriers, in particular that of the carrier being acquired and/or the smallest of the merging parts, which may have served as a stepping stone for the largest carrier's repositioning in the market.

In terms of policy implications, the paper sheds light on the potential consequences that adjustments in airline business models and/or consolidations may bring in terms of network design. While the paper does not necessarily bring any novel results that would significantly shift regulation in this domain, it does support findings from previous research in the areas of network design, airport

access and airline consolidation. Some of the issues that regulators and planners might want to consider include:

- *The effects of innovative business models on the development and upgrading of airports:* This is illustrated by the surge of Azul airlines in the Campinas/Viracopos airport, a traditional air cargo terminal and second-tier airport in terms of passenger numbers. Azul's blend of low fares together with a connection oriented network structure were key for the increased passenger numbers at this airport, which witnessed a ten-fold growth in the period from 2008 to 2014, following its choice as the airline's main hub (Source: data from ANAC's Air Transport Statistical Database, 2008-2014). As a result, not only was Viracopos' otherwise less sought-after infrastructure better utilized, but this initiative also made it sufficiently viable and attractive for inclusion in part of an airport privatization process that took place in Brazil.
- *The role of business models on the viability of new airport infrastructure:* The business models of potential airlines to be attracted to a new airport must be taken into account before the actual construction of the necessary infrastructure, as the airport's location and its design can favor (or hinder) particular business models (Papatheodorou and Lei, 2006; Collins et al., 2010; Gillen and Hazledine, 2015). A shift from a 'build and they will come' mindset is critical for future airport planning at a macro/national level.
- *The effects of consolidations on airport infrastructure development:* Airline mergers and acquisitions, along with changes in network structure design, may impose severe risks associated with the forecast of airport infrastructure development, as the consolidation of networks in fewer, more concentrated hubs can lead to the abrupt closure of individual routes with significant impacts to airports - especially regional ones. Policymakers, particularly those responsible for air passenger subsidy implementation, should monitor changes in airline business models to make sure that vulnerable communities will not be affected (Thompson, 2002; Baker and Donnet, 2012).

6.1. Limitations and future research

We point out that our results are confined to the experience of the Brazilian air transportation industry, particularly associated with a snapshot of the period 2001-2018. Due to this setting, we have benefited from analyzing this industry from the beginning of its deregulation process. We were able to observe distinct business model archetypes, as Brazilian airlines were still tweaking their operational characteristics. More broadly, however, as companies constantly adapt to the market,

archetypes become harder to be found – not surprisingly, they themselves become subject to changes.

In this way, future research from a network design point of view in contexts such as the US and Europe, where a larger array of carriers is available, could provide an interesting ramification, possibly put into practice by the creation of archetypes as ‘external constructs’. Although conformation of these carriers to business model archetypes would probably be manifested to a lesser extent, given the comparatively longer period of time since their inceptions following deregulation in these markets, ‘external archetypes’ could be formed from a set of carriers by capturing their mean behavior, enabling them to be as free from idiosyncratic influences as possible. We believe that further investigation into this issue should be conducted, with econometric models aiming at a better understanding of the way carriers adapt their businesses to their environments and to their rivals, as well as how they may exploit the opportunities set out by consolidations in deregulated markets.

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Appendix - Description of data and variables

We define a route as a directional city-pair market associated with the movement of scheduled revenue passengers in a given month. The dataset consists of 2,613 distinct domestic routes in Brazil and 154,281 route/year observations overall, with 40,292 observations used for the 1st methodological step and 113,989 observations used in the 2nd step. Our main data sources are the National Civil Aviation Agency (ANAC) and the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE).

The variables and controls utilized in the 1st step regressions are the following:

- DIST is a variable measuring the Vincenty distance in kilometers between the endpoints of route i . This is an average value, as some cities are associated with more than one airport. It is included to assess the impact of a route's distance on a given archetype's route selection criteria. Furthermore, this variable is also employed for capturing the use of connecting flights on these archetypes' network configurations.
- DIST² is a variable measuring the *square* of the distance in kilometers between the endpoints of route i . This variable is considered to allow for a possibly nonlinear relationship between the route's length and the archetype's presence.
- INCOME = $\max(GDPPC_{a_o}; GDPPC_{a_d})$ is a function with inputs corresponding to the GDPs *per capita* (in billion R\$) associated with the origin and destination cities of a given route i at a given period t , pertaining to archetype a 's network ($GDPPC_{a_o}$ and $GDPPC_{a_d}$, respectively). This function returns the maximal value between these two quantities, with lagged values of 12 months being employed (to better represent the network planning horizon of carriers). It is adjusted by a deflator based on the Broad Consumer Price Index (IPCA), to a value comparable to January 2019. For the computation of the GDPs, we considered the entire geographic area of a mesoregion as defined by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), with São Paulo cities having additional mesoregions. Source: (IBGE).
- NETWORK = $\max(D_{a_o}; D_{a_d})$ is a function with inputs corresponding to the number of destinations associated with the origin and destination airports of a given route i at a given period t , pertaining to archetype a 's network (D_{a_o} and D_{a_d} , respectively). Similar to the previous variable, this function returns the maximal value between these two quantities lagged by 12 months. It is used to assess the centrality of a set of airports for archetype a 's network.

- Regional dummies, equal to $\mathbb{1}_{r_o}(i)$ and $\mathbb{1}_{r_d}(i)$, are sets of controls for origin and destination regions $r_o, r_d \in R = \{CW, NE, NW, SE, SW\}$. For a fixed origin region r_o , the function $\mathbb{1}_{r_o}(i)$ takes on the value 1 (one) if route i has its origin pertaining to it ($i \in r_o$) and 0 (zero) otherwise. Destination regions are defined similarly.
- Seasonality and time trend terms are also considered in order to control for periods of expansion and contraction of these archetypes' networks.

The variables and controls utilized in the 2nd step regressions are the following:

- PR_FSC, PR_LCC and PR_RGC are the predictions for the latent expected profit variables associated with the “FSC”, “LCC” and “RGC” archetypes, respectively. These predictions are obtained from the 1st stage *probit (logit)* regressions, associated with the construction of archetypical mentalities. Together with their interactions with a time trend variable and with a merger¹ dummy (in the cases of Gol's, Azul's and LATAM's models), these variables will allow us to infer to which business model archetype(s) (if any) each Brazilian carrier have converged, or to which business model(s) they remained faithful. This will reflect each company's business model blend and its mutational process, as described in **H1**.
- MERGER is a carrier-specific dummy variable, set equal to ‘1’ (one) in periods after the corresponding airline's merger - which would be 2007 for Gol's merger with Varig, 2010 for TAM's merger with LAN and 2012 for Azul's merger with Trip.
- PR_FSC \times MERGER, PR_LCC \times MERGER and PR_RGC \times MERGER are interactions of the MERGER variable with the predictions for the latent expected profits, accounting for the impact of these disruptive events on the propensity of a carrier to adhere to (or avoid) a given business model archetype.
- TREND is an increasing discrete linear variable, set to ‘0’ (zero) at the beginning of the estimation period of the second stage, January 2006. The rationale for using this variable in this stage is that the studied companies could appear to be converging or imitating each other when, in reality, all of them could be only expanding their networks. This being the case, these companies could not possibly shy away from operating the same markets as their competitors.²

¹ To simplify the exposition, hereafter our use of the term “merger” will comprise both mergers and acquisitions.

² Notice that this period does not comprehend observations utilized for the construction of the archetype's mentalities.

- $PR_FSC \times TREND$, $PR_LCC \times TREND$ and $PR_RGC \times TREND$ are interactions of the TREND variable with the predictions for the latent expected profits, allowing for the investigation of how carriers' behaviors changed over time (their mutational processes). In this manner, we enhance the model's flexibility for capturing the evolution of a given carrier's archetypical blend during the period comprised in the dataset.
- Regional dummies and seasonality controls, as previously defined in the first stage models, are included here as well.

Below are descriptive statistics of the main variables in the models.

Table A1 - Descriptive statistics of the main variables

Variable	Nr. Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
DIST	40,292	0.999	0.785	0.040	3.502
INCOME	40,292	2.438	1.263	0.335	8.098
NETWORK (FSC)	40,292	17.080	12.617	0	47
NETWORK (LCC)	40,292	7.412	7.994	0	32
NETWORK (RGC)	40,292	1.540	3.824	0	19
FSC Archetype	40,292	0.397	0.489	0	1
LCC Archetype	40,292	0.244	0.430	0	1
RGC Archetype	40,292	0.046	0.209	0	1
Azul Airlines	113,989	0.296	0.456	0	1
Gol Airlines	113,989	0.498	0.500	0	1
Avianca Airlines	113,989	0.134	0.341	0	1
LATAM Airlines	113,989	0.368	0.482	0	1
MERGER (Trip)	113,989	0.469	0.499	0	1
MERGER (Varig)	113,989	0.900	0.300	0	1
MERGER (LAN)	113,989	0.619	0.486	0	1

¹ We also mention results by Evangelho, Huse and Linhares (2005), indicating the role of culture in the preference for FSCs by business travelers of large organizations, and those of Huse and Evangelho (2007), which suggest that these passengers tend to reassess their valuation of some product attributes more favorably to LCCs after having experienced their services.

² “*Ryanair's business class*” – The Economist, Feb. 28, 2013.

³ “*Norwegian might still transform long-haul flying*” – The Economist, Jul. 13, 2017.

⁴ “*With its Cost Advantage Eroded, Southwest Forced to Aim for International Markets*” – Forbes, Nov. 2, 2016.

⁵ For an examination of the connection between airline networks and their business models, the reader is referred to Gillen and Morrison (2005). Moreover, an interesting account of particular characteristics of point-to-point network planning may be found in Faust et al., (2017).

⁶ “*Flag carriers try to stay competitive by learning from the budget Airlines*” – The New York Times, Nov. 5, 2008.

⁷ This could lead to a continuous cycle of convergence towards profitable differentiation strategies. An example would be that of a set of firms first complying with a traditional LCC business model in a given market. While some firms may prosper, the less cost-efficient ones would be forced to deviate from this template, with some of those differentiation strategies turning out to be successful. These strategies would, in turn, be replicated, giving rise to an equilibrium around new (hybrid) business models, ultimately making room for ‘pure’ LCCs (not necessarily cost-efficient) to thrive, insinuating a return to the starting point. The emergence of the so-called ‘ultra low-cost carriers’ (ULCC) in recent years, exemplified by carriers such as Spirit Airlines and Allegiant Air, can be used to support this claim.

⁸ We note that, in their research, Southwest was the only airline that successfully conformed to its proposed integrated strategy (of both cost leadership and product differentiation).

⁹ From operational characteristics, evidence of business model convergence has also been reported concerning airlines' unit costs (Tsoukalas et al., 2008). Interestingly, the same does not appear to have occurred for aircraft ground times (Lange et al., 2019).

¹⁰ As examples, we cite the cases of airlines such as EasyJet and Air Berlin. These firms' business models were initially based on strict low-cost practices, being later readapted with the implementation of typical features of established full-service carriers.

¹¹ Gol and TAM used to split almost evenly the largest airports and densest routes in the Brazilian domestic market. By that time, these companies benefitted from limited competition, stemming from either smaller mainline or regional carriers.

¹² Gol Intelligent Airlines Inc. (30 Apr 2018) United States Securities and Exchange Commission - FORM 20-F. Available at www.sec.gov.

¹³ Azul S.A. (30 Apr 2019) United States Securities and Exchange Commission - FORM 20-F. Available at www.sec.gov.

¹⁴ As suggested by their public statements, found at Avianca's website (www.avianca.com.br) and Azul S.A. (27 Apr 2018) United States Securities and Exchange Commission - FORM 20-F (available at www.sec.gov).